

EVALUATION OF INTERFACIAL THERMAL RESISTANCE OF AL-ALN PARTICLE DISPERSED COMPOSITES BY USING IMAGE-BASED CALCULATION

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial thermal resistance in Al-AlN composites was evaluated by comparing the measured thermal conductivity and the calculated thermal conductivity. Al-AlN composites was fabricated by spark plasma sintering with changing the volume fraction of AlN from 10% to 40%. Effective thermal conductivity was measured with the steady state thermal conductivity measuring device. Effective thermal conductivity was also calculated by using SEM image and the measured relative density. Comparing the measured thermal conductivity and the calculated thermal conductivity, the interfacial thermal resistance at the Al-AlN interface was evaluated and in the range from 1.7×10^{-9} to 7.1×10^{-9} ($\text{m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$).

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with the development of information technology and automotive industries, it is expected that miniaturization and high integration of portable information terminals and power electronic devices will further progress, and expectations for efficient heat dissipation and heat exchange technology is increasing. Metal matrix composites (MMCs) are expected as high thermal conductivity materials to solve this problem. Although MMCs have advantages for thermal management, the interfacial thermal resistance between the matrix and the reinforcement is one of the problems. The different mechanism of heat conduction between metals and ceramics causes the interfacial thermal resistance. The heat in metals is transmitted by lattice vibrations (phonons) and free electrons. On the other hand, the heat in ceramics is transmitted by the only lattice vibrations. In the MMCs, reflection and scattering occur at the interface of two different substances, and interfacial thermal resistance greatly affects thermal conductivity of composite materials. However, quantitative discussions on the degree of the influence of interfacial thermal resistance is not enough. AlN particle is one of candidates as a reinforcing material because it exhibits high elastic modulus, hardness and good thermal conductivity. In this study, interfacial thermal resistance in Al-AlN composites was evaluated by comparing the measured thermal conductivity and the calculated thermal conductivity, where the calculations were carried out by using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image.

2 PROCEDURE

2.1 Experimental Procedure

Al powder with an average particle size of 3 μm and purity 99.9% (High Purity Chemical Laboratory Co., Ltd.) was used as the matrix. AlN powder with an average particle size of 2 μm and purity 99.9% (High Purity Chemical Laboratory Co., Ltd.) was used as the reinforcement. Al powder and AlN powder was blended in ethanol for 4 hours with a V-type mixer (50 rpm). Al -10vol.% AlN, Al -20vol.% AlN and Al -40vol.% AlN green compacts were prepared. The sample was consolidated by spark plasma sintering (SPS) under the vacuum of 10^{-2} Pa. After pre-sintering for 400s using DC pulsed discharge at a pressure of 15 MPa, main sintering was carried out at the pressure of 50 MPa, the

sintering temperature of 550 ° C and the holding time of 600 s. Measurement of relative density with Archimedes method, structure observation by SEM, measurement of effective thermal conductivity with the steady state thermal conductivity measuring device[1] were performed.

2.2 Calculation Procedure

The effective thermal conductivity was calculated by using SEM image acquired from the fabricated sample. Image processing techniques such as smoothing, thresholding, morphology transformation were combined to binarize the SEM image. The finite volume method was used to calculate two-dimensional temperature distributions. Simulation code can take into account of the coefficient of heat transfer at the interface [2]. Temperature of element i, j after Δt , $T_{i,j}^{n+1}$, can be calculated by

$$T_{i,j}^{n+1} = T_{i,j}^n + \frac{\Delta t}{\rho c} \left(\frac{q_{i+1,j}^n - q_{i-1,j}^n}{\Delta x} + \frac{q_{i,j+1}^n - q_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y} \right) \quad (1)$$

where $T_{i,j}^n$ is the present temperature of the noticed element i, j , Δx and Δy are size of element, ρ is the density and c is the specific heat.

When the type of a neighbor element is same as the noticed elements, the heat flux q^n is calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} q_{i+1,j}^n &= \lambda_{i,j} \left(\frac{T_{i+1,j}^n - T_{i,j}^n}{\Delta x} \right), & q_{i-1,j}^n &= \lambda_{i,j} \left(\frac{T_{i,j}^n - T_{i-1,j}^n}{\Delta x} \right), \\ q_{i,j+1}^n &= \lambda_{i,j} \left(\frac{T_{i,j+1}^n - T_{i,j}^n}{\Delta y} \right), & q_{i,j-1}^n &= \lambda_{i,j} \left(\frac{T_{i,j}^n - T_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $T_{i+1,j}^n$, $T_{i-1,j}^n$, $T_{i,j+1}^n$ and $T_{i,j-1}^n$ are temperatures of the neighbor elements and $\lambda_{i,j}$ is the thermal conductivity of the noticed element. The thermal conductivity of AlN was fixed to 195 W/(mK). Because relative density of the samples fabricated in this study is not one hundred percent, thermal conductivity of the matrix with pores [3] was calculated by

$$\lambda_m = \frac{1}{4} \left[\lambda_p (3v_p - 1) + \lambda_s (3v_s - 1) + \left(\left[\lambda_p (3v_p - 1) + \lambda_s (3v_s - 1) \right]^2 + 8\lambda_p \lambda_s \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (3)$$

where λ_p and λ_s are the thermal conductivity of the pore and the solid, respectively, and v_p and v_s are the volume fraction of the pore and the solid, respectively. λ_p was set to 0 W/(mK) and λ_s for pure Aluminum was set to 214 W/(mK), which was determined by the measurement of a sintered pure Aluminum sample. In the equation (3), the pores were assumed to be distributed homogeneously in the Aluminum matrix.

When the type of a neighbor element is different from the noticed element, heat flux q^n is calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} q_{i+1,j}^n &= h(T_{i+1,j} - T_{i,j}), & q_{i-1,j}^n &= h(T_{i,j} - T_{i-1,j}), \\ q_{i,j+1}^n &= h(T_{i,j+1} - T_{i,j}), & q_{i,j-1}^n &= h(T_{i,j} - T_{i,j-1}), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where h is the coefficient of heat transfer between Al and AlN. The series of calculations were carried out by changing the coefficient of heat transfer, h .

Fig. 1 shows schematics of simulation model. Image part is sandwiched by heat sources. The size of image part was 480×410 elements, and the size of heat sources was 5×410 elements ($N_L = N_R = 5$). The adiabatic boundary conditions were applied parallel to the heat flow direction and the periodic boundary condition was applied perpendicular to the heat flow direction. The temperature of the left edge of the elements was set to 301 K and the temperature of the remaining elements was set to 300 K as initial condition. The temperature of the left and right sides of the elements was fixed and the temperature of the remaining elements was iteratively updated until average variation of temperature of each element was lower than 10^{-12} , and steady state of temperature distributions was obtained. Effective thermal conductivity of composite, λ_{eff} , was evaluated from steady state of temperature distributions using following equation.

$$\lambda_{eff} = \frac{\lambda_{Al}\Delta T_{12}N_x}{\Delta T_{LR} + N_L\Delta T_{12} - N_R\Delta T_{12}} \quad (5)$$

where ΔT_{LR} is temperature difference between left and right side and ΔT_{12} is the average of temperature difference between first and second column. N_L and N_R are number of elements of right and left heat source, respectively. N_x is number of elements of image part.

Figure 1: Schematics of simulation model.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure and effective thermal conductivity of composites

Fig. 2 (a), (b) and (c) shows the microstructure of Al-10vol.%AlN, Al-20vol.%AlN and Al-40vol.%AlN composites, respectively. Table 1 shows the measured effective thermal conductivity and relative density of the fabricated sample. The effective thermal conductivity decreased with increasing the volume fraction of AlN.

Figure 2: Microstructure of (a) Al-10vol.%AlN, (b) Al-20vol.%AlN and (c) Al-40vol.%AlN composites.

Sample	10vol.%	20vol.%	40vol.%
Effective thermal conductivity [W/(mK)]	178.4	175.4	104.0
Relative Density [%]	95.2	98.6	96.4

Table 1: Effective thermal conductivity and relative density of Al-AlN composites.

3.2 Effective thermal conductivity calculated by image-based calculations

Microstructure images were binarized as shown in Fig. 3 and simulation cell was created by sandwiching the binarized image with heat sources. The element size was determined by scale size, and the element size of Al-10vol.%AlN and Al-20vol.%AlN was 63.33 nm and the element size of Al-

40vol.%AlN was 47.3 nm. The series of calculations were carried out by changing the coefficient of heat transfer, h , at the Al-AlN interface. Fig. 4 shows the calculated effective thermal conductivity respect to the coefficient of heat transfer. Dashed lines represent the calculated effective thermal conductivity from SEM image. Horizontal solid line represents the measured effective thermal conductivity.

Figure 3: Binarized image of (a) Al-10vol.%AlN, (b) Al-20vol.%AlN and (c) Al-40vol.%AlN composites.

Figure 4: Calculated effective thermal conductivity respect to the coefficient of heat transfer at the Al-AlN interface.

Devis et al. [4] have suggested the effective thermal conductivity, λ_{eff} , with taking into account the interfacial thermal resistance, R_{Bd} . λ_{eff} is calculated by

$$\lambda_{eff} = \frac{[\lambda_r(1+2\alpha)+2\lambda_m]+2\phi[\lambda_r(1-\alpha)-\lambda_m]}{[\lambda_r(1+2\alpha)+2\lambda_m]-\phi[\lambda_r(1-\alpha)-\lambda_m]}\lambda_m, \quad \alpha = \frac{R_{Bd}\lambda_m}{a}, \quad R_{Bd} = \frac{1}{h} \quad (6)$$

where ϕ is the volume fraction of particles, a is the average size of particles, λ_r is the thermal conductivity of the particles and λ_m is the thermal conductivity of the matrix which was calculated by equation (3), and h is the coefficient of heat transfer at the interface. Dash-dotted lines represent the variance of the effective thermal conductivity calculated by equation (6). The point of intersection of calculated and measured value indicates the coefficient of heat transfer between Al and AlN, and the coefficients of heat transfer can be evaluated by this kind analysis. Table 2 compares the coefficients of heat transfer evaluated by the present image-based calculation and the model of Davis et al. The coefficients of heat transfer of the present work is larger than that of Davis et al. The coefficients of heat transfer can be calculated by Phonon diffuse mismatch model (DMM) [5].

$$h_{BD}^{DMM} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_j v_{1,j} \int_0^{\omega_{c,j}} \alpha_1(\omega) \hbar \omega D_{1,j}(\omega) \frac{\partial n(\omega, T)}{\partial T} d\omega \quad (7)$$

where ω is the cutoff frequency, $D(\omega)$ is the density of states, $n(\omega, T)$ is the Bose-Einstein phonon distribution function, ω is the phonon frequency, v is the phonon velocity, $\alpha(\omega)$ the phonon transmission probability, and \hbar is Dirac's constant. Table 2 also shows the coefficients of heat transfer calculated by equation (7). The coefficients of heat transfer of the present work is equivalent to that of Phonon DMM. Because interfacial misfit is not considered in the phonon DMM model, influence of interfacial misfits at the interface is small in the fabricated sample. Finally, interfacial thermal resistances evaluated in the present work are shown in Table 2.

	10vol.%	20vol.%	40vol.%
Present work, h [W/(m ² K)]	1.9×10^8	5.8×10^8	1.4×10^8
Davis et al., h [W/(m ² K)]	-	9.2×10^7	2.4×10^6
Phonon DMM, h [W/(m ² K)]	4.84×10^8		
Interfacial thermal resistance [(m ² K)/W]	5.3×10^{-9}	1.7×10^{-9}	7.1×10^{-9}

Table 2: Coefficient of heat transfer (h) at the Al-AlN interface and interfacial thermal resistance evaluated in the present work.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Interfacial thermal resistance in Al-AlN composites was evaluated by comparing the measured thermal conductivity and the calculated thermal conductivity. Al-10vol.%AlN, Al-20vol.%AlN and Al-40vol.%AlN composites were fabricated by SPS. Effective thermal conductivities of the samples were measured with the steady state thermal conductivity measuring device. Effective thermal conductivities were calculated by using SEM image and the measured relative density. Comparing the measured thermal conductivity and the calculated thermal conductivity, the interfacial thermal resistance at the Al-AlN interface was evaluated as 5.3×10^{-9} (m²K)/W for Al-10vol.%AlN composite, 1.7×10^{-9} (m²K)/W for Al-20vol.%AlN composite and 7.1×10^{-9} (m²K)/W for Al-40vol.%AlN composite.

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